

Cube Subtraction Strategy in Reconfigurable Hardware SAT Solvers

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Abstract

The majority of the existing reconfigurable hardware SAT solvers employ some variation of the Davis-Putnam algorithm; we propose a new algorithm for organizing the search in SAT Solvers best suited to reconfigurable architectures due to its vector-like operations. Its essence is to view each negated clause as a cube in the n -dimensional Boolean search space, and realizing that each of these clause-cubes denotes a sub-region of the search space where no satisfying assignments can be found. Starting from the universal cube, which represents the whole space, we systematically subtract all clause-cubes until we end up with a satisfying cube or an empty cube if the SAT formula is unsatisfiable. The algorithm for cube subtraction is the D-Sharp algorithm. We implemented this strategy in the well-known zChaff SAT solver. Improvements in execution time and number of aborted instances have been observed for the new algorithm. The test suite includes several instances from IBM-CNF BMC and Microprocessor's Formal Verification benchmarks.

1. Introduction

Propositional Satisfiability (SAT) is a well-known NP-complete problem with theoretical and practical significance, and with extensive applications in many fields of Computer Science and Engineering, including Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Electronic Design Automation (EDA). The SAT formulation can efficiently solve large hardware problems, including microprocessor verification [1], bounded [2] and unbounded model checking. As a result, practical SAT solvers have received considerable attention.

Many of the SAT solvers, which participated in the last SAT contest [3], aim at finding a satisfying assignment by variable splitting. Search algorithms of that kind are mainly descendants of the Davis Putnam Loveland and Logemann algorithm (DPLL) [4]. The majority of the existing reconfigurable hardware SAT solvers employ some variation of the Davis-Putnam algorithm and a survey of systems and algorithms is presented detailed in [5]. In present-day software SAT solvers, advanced search techniques (such as nonchronological backtracking, dynamic clause addition and restarts) are employed. However,

up to now, hardware SAT solvers have largely ignored these techniques. The only exception to this is the SAT satisfier of Zhong [6]. The main reason is that sophisticated decision and backtracking techniques require complex data structures that favour software over hardware implementations.

Recent research has highlighted the importance of the analysis of clauses together with variables, which are empirically successful on real-world industrial instances. The Variable State Independent Decaying Sum (VSIDS) of zChaff [7] scores variables for locality centric decision-making. In Berkmin [8], the authors claimed that VSIDS alone is not sufficiently dynamic, and proposed organizing the conflict clauses in a list, picking the next decision variable from the top-most unsatisfied clause in the list. Looking at the SAT contest results [3] we can see the advantages of clause-based decision heuristics.

Our approach also exploits decision taking based on clause analysis. It is based on an algorithm briefly described in [9] and deemed inefficient. However, we show here how this idea can be made practical. After backtracking, we identify a problematic clause of the decision variable in question, and we continuously insist on variables from this clause. If more conflicts are found we remain in this clause until no more conflicts are caused or we backtrack past it. We call this technique the D-Sharp Strategy as the basics of it relies on the sharp (#) operator for cube subtraction.

One of the benefits of this approach is that it tries to identify a clause or a group of clauses that can lead to unsatisfiability, if the problem is UNSAT, or which are hard to satisfy if the problem is SAT. We think that the data structure and the operations associated to the D-Sharp algorithms can be vector oriented, what is best suited to reconfigurable hardware implementation.

This paper is organized as follows. The next section provides basic definitions. In section 3 we introduce the D-Sharp algorithm and how it is applied to SAT. In section 4 we show the integration in a DPLL solver and in section 5 we report results. This is followed by conclusion and future work.

2. Basic definitions

This section introduces the notational framework used in this paper. Propositional variables are

denoted x_1, \dots, x_n and can be assigned truth values 0 (or F) or 1 (or T).

A literal l is either a variable x_i or its negation $\neg x_i$. A clause w is a disjunction of literals and a CNF formula ϕ is a conjunction of clauses. A clause is said to be satisfied if at least one of its literals assumes value 1, unsatisfied if all of its literals assume value 0, unit if all but one literal assumes value 0, and unresolved otherwise. Literals with no assigned truth-value are said to be free literals.

A formula is said to be satisfied if all its clauses are satisfied and is said unsatisfied if at least one clause is unsatisfied. A truth assignment for a formula is a set of assigned variables and their corresponding truth-values.

The goal of a complete SAT solver is to determine an assignment to the variables that turns the SAT formula true or to prove that no such assignment exists, in which case the formula is unsatisfiable.

A cube is a Boolean expression containing a conjunction of literals (logical AND). It may be defined as: $c = (c_0 c_1 \dots c_{n-1})$, where $c_i = \{ 0, 1 \text{ or } X \}$, being X a *don't care*. A cube obtained from negating a clause is called here a clause-cube, what can be done by negating both sides of a clause getting a Disjunctive Normal Form. A cube c_i can be subtracted from a cube c_j and the result is a set of cubes that cover all the minterms in c_j but not in c_i .

Cube subtraction is normally denoted by the sharp operator (#). If the subtraction operation is defined so that the result is a set of disjoint cubes we denote the operator as Disjoint Sharp or *D-Sharp*. The algorithm we use for performing the D-Sharp operation has the same basic ideas of the one proposed in [10][11] for faults in Programmable Logic Arrays (PLA's), and which is formalized next.

D-Sharp definition. Let $a = (a_{n-1} a_{n-2} \dots a_1 a_0)$ and $b = (b_{n-1} b_{n-2} \dots b_1 b_0)$. Then $a \# b$ is defined as follows: $a \# b = C$, where $C = \{ c^{n-1}, c^{n-2}, \dots, c^1, c^0 \}$ and each $c^i = (a_{n-1} \beta b_{n-1}) (a_{n-2} \beta b_{n-2}) \dots (a_{i+1} \beta b_{i+1}) (a_i \gamma b_i) (a_{i-1}) \dots (a_1) (a_0)$. The operators β and γ are defined in Figure 1.

β	0	1	X
0	0	\emptyset	0
1	\emptyset	1	1
X	0	1	X

Fig. 1: Definition of operators β and γ

if any term of c^i is evaluated as \emptyset then c^i is evaluated as \emptyset (empty cube). The algorithm can be best understood through an example:

Let $a = (10XX)$ and $b = (10X1)$

$C = (a \# b) = \{ c^3, c^2, c^1, c^0 \}$

$c^3 = (a_3 \gamma b_3)(a_2)(a_1)(a_0) = (1 \gamma 1)0XX = \emptyset 0XX = \emptyset$

$c^2 = (a_3 \beta b_3)(a_2 \gamma b_2)(a_1)(a_0) = (1 \beta 1)(0 \gamma 0)XX = 1 \emptyset XX = \emptyset$

$c^1 = (a_3 \beta b_3)(a_2 \beta b_2)(a_1 \gamma b_1)(a_0)$

$= (1 \beta 1)(0 \beta 0)(X \gamma X)X = 10 \emptyset X = \emptyset$

$c^0 = (a_3 \beta b_3)(a_2 \beta b_2)(a_1 \beta b_1)(a_0 \gamma b_0)$

Fig. 2: D-Sharp tree example

$= (1 \beta 1)(0 \beta 0)(X \beta X)(X \gamma 1) = 10X0$

then $C = (a \# b) = \{ (10X0) \}$, as showed in Fig. 2.

3. D-Sharp algorithm in a SAT solver

In order to understand how to construct a D-Sharp SAT solver, we start with a simple DPLL like description, without any further improvement such as non-chronological backtracking, clause learning, restarts or locality.

For a formula $\phi = w_1 \wedge w_2 \wedge \dots \wedge w_m$, we negate both sides and apply De Morgan's laws getting a Disjunctive Normal Form (DNF) formula $\neg \phi = c^1 \vee c^2 \vee \dots \vee c^m$. The disjunction of clause-cubes represents all the regions of the search space where no satisfying assignments can be found.

When we successively apply the sharp operation between the current search space and each clause-cube, we finish with the solution subspace of formula ϕ .

Starting with the universal cube u , which denotes the whole search space, ie.: $u = (u_1 u_2 \dots u_n)$ with each u_i literal having value X , the solution cube set S_ϕ is given by:

$$S_\phi = (((u \# c_1) \# c_2) \# \dots) \# c_m.$$

After each D-Sharp operation we are left with disjoint search subspaces. The remaining clauses must be subtracted from each of these subspaces. The choice of a disjoint subtraction operation avoids repeating the search in each subspace since they have null intersection by definition.

The algorithm of a basic D-Sharp based SAT solver is explained next. The solver is defined recursively and is first called from the main routine with arguments $u = (XX \dots X)$ as the current search space, and level = 0. The pseudo code is given in Figure 3.

The Decide() function is responsible for choosing the next clause-cube to be subtracted. The Dsharp() function executes the D-Sharp operation between the current search subspace and the clause-cube elected by Decide().

```

int Solve (current_space, level){
  if (level == last level)
    return (SAT);
  chosen_clause_cube = Decide ();
  C=Dsharp(current_solution, chosen_clause_cube)
  For each cube c_i in C {
    solver_return= Solve(c_i, level+1);
    if (solver_return = SAT)
      return (SAT);
  }
  return(UNSAT);
}

```

Figure 3: D-Sharp based SAT solver pseudo code

Like in a DPLL-based SAT solver, rules for reaching the final solution faster may be applied. A conflict is reached when a clause-cube covers the current search space. In this situation we backtrack. If a clause-cube has null intersection with the current search subspace there is no need to apply the D-Sharp operation, the result is the current search subspace itself. Finally, an implication (or Boolean Constraint Propagation) happens when the D-Sharp operation produces a single cube as the result. As can be seen, the set C in this pseudo code may suffer from memory blow-up, however it is left this way just for better understanding.

The D-Sharp based SAT solving algorithm can be better understood using a simple CNF formula example: $\phi = (\neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2 \vee \neg x_4) \wedge (x_1 \vee \neg x_2 \vee x_3) \wedge (x_1 \vee \neg x_3 \vee \neg x_4)$

Applying De Morgan laws to the formula we have:
 $\neg \phi = (x_1 \wedge \neg x_2 \wedge x_4) \vee (\neg x_1 \wedge x_2 \wedge \neg x_3) \vee (\neg x_1 \wedge x_3 \wedge x_4)$
 In vector cube notation we have:

$$\neg \phi = (10X1) \vee (010X) \vee (0X11)$$

Now starting with $u=(XXXX)$, which means any assignment for (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) , taking the first clause to subtract and applying the D-Sharp algorithm we get the result: $(XXXX) \# (10X1) = (0XXX) \vee (11XX) \vee (10X0)$, which has three disjoints search subspaces. Note that the search sub-spaces have null intersection to avoid unnecessary search in overlapped regions, which justifies the use of the D-Sharp operator.

The complete search tree for the example is illustrated in Figure 4. Each level of the tree corresponds to the D-Sharp operation between the current search subspace and the clause-cubes, in the same order in which they are given. Note that, unlike the DPLL algorithm, the resulting search tree is not binary. However this tree can be superimposed in a DPLL binary tree, it allows us to benefit from all techniques that have been developed for SAT solvers: BCP, decision heuristics, non-chronological backtracking and clause learning, as explained in the next section.

Figure 4: Complete search tree of a basic D-Sharp based SAT solver

4. Integrating D-Sharp in a DPLL Solver

To insert the D-Sharp algorithm into a DPLL-based solver, the D-Sharp operation defined in section 2 for a DNF formulation must be adapted to work into a CNF formulation. This is done by assigning the literals in a clause to obtain, in each tentative assignment, the cubes c^i that appear in the D-Sharp definition when subtracting a cube that represents a clause yet to satisfy from the cube that corresponds to the current assignment of variables. We illustrate this with an example: Let ϕ be a single clause formula given by $\phi = (\neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2 \vee \neg x_3)$. ϕ is converted to DNF as showed in section 3 as:

$\neg \phi = (x_1 \wedge x_2 \wedge x_3) = (111)$. Starting with $u=(XXX)$ and performing the D-Sharp operation we get:

$$(XXX) \# (111) = (0XX) \vee (10X) \vee (110).$$

The assignment $x_1=1$ is the same as the first disjoint search subspace (0XX), the assignment to $x_1=0$ and $x_2=1$ is the same as the second search subspace (10X), the assignment $x_1=0, x_2=0$ and $x_3=1$ is the same as the third search subspace (110). In a formula with more than one clause we may have conflicts after variable assignments. Only at this moment we associate the variable with a clause, and the next variable to be decided must come from this clause. To reproduce the tentative assignments as give by the D-Sharp algorithm, the next assignment is obtained by toggling the current decision variable and assigning a satisfying value to another variable from the same clause. In order to integrate the D-Sharp algorithm in a DPLL SAT solver we inserted changes in the clause database, in the conflict analysis, decision branching and in the clause deletion procedures.

5. Experimental results

We implemented a D-Sharp based SAT solver using the last version of the zChaff solver, downloaded from [12] as *zChaff-2004.11.15*. This version won the SAT 2004 contest [3] in the Industrial Category. All the experiments were done on a Pentium 4 machine at 2.0 GHz with 2Gbytes of memory on Linux.

The examples in Table 1 are part of the IBM-CNF BMC benchmarks. The complete benchmark set can be downloaded from [13]. Table 1 compares zChaff-2004 with our D-Sharp approach in terms of performance (CPU time) and robustness (number of aborted instances). The column "Inst." shows the number of instances used, the time-out was set to 5000 seconds. From these results it is clear that the D-Sharp algorithm performs better and is more robust, especially for industrial families. The results where the CPU time or number of aborted instances is lower for the D-Sharp approach are highlighted in bold font. The same situation repeats on Table 2,

which is generated from logic circuits problems. The SAT problems are derived from formal verification of superscalar and VLIW microprocessors, buggy variants of VLIW microprocessors, liveness of single-issue pipelined and dual-issue superscalar DLX processor. Some of these benchmarks were used in the SAT competition. The complete series of benchmarks and descriptions can be downloaded from [14]. The time-out was set to 5000 seconds

Table 1: Results on IBM-CNF, BMC series.

Class of benchmark (IBM-BMC) IBM-FV	Inst	zChaff (2004)		Dsharp	
		Time (sec.)	Aborts	Time (sec.)	Aborts
2004_01	11	10204	0	5633	0
2004_07	11	209	0	93	0
2004_01_11	11	24512	3	23963	3
2004_2_14	11	10119	1	9504	0
2004_18	11	32730	6	30101	5
2004_20	11	29702	5	28349	5
2004_23	11	32238	6	30198	4
2002_01	17	20367	6	20346	5
2002_02_1_1	17	2064	0	1921	0
2002_02_1_2	17	1454	0	1336	0
2002_02_1_3	17	3163	1	3201	1
2002_02_1_4	17	132	0	72	0
2002_02_3_1	17	731	0	274	0
2002_02_3_2	17	84	0	123	0
2002_02_3_3	17	420	0	337	0
2002_02_3_4	17	257	0	39.9	0
2002_02_3_5	17	235	0	227	0
2002_02_3_6	17	320	0	70	0
2002_03_	17	18656	5	15508	2
2002_04_	17	16099	4	17039	4
2002_05_	17	11803	2	12072	2
2002_06_	17	19257	4	20223	4
2002_07_	17	1062	0	161	0
2002_09_	17	14.6	0	5.9	0

Table 2: Microprocessors Formal Verifications results.

Class of benchmarks	Inst	zChaff (2004)		Dsharp	
		Time (sec.)	Aborts	Time (sec.)	Aborts
sss.1.0_cnf	48	8.9	0	4.4	0
sss.1.0a_cnf	9	4.5	0	4.0	0
sss-sat-1.0	100	121	0	112	0
vliw-sat-1.0	100	2033	0	1807	0
fvp-unsat_1.0	4	108.3	0	100.5	0
fvp_unsat2.0	22	1756	0	1780	0
Livenessat10	10	40724	6	32653	5

6. Conclusion and future works

This paper describes an algorithm for SAT solving using cube subtraction following up a suggestion in [9]. A thorough software evaluation of the algorithm is presented, showing that it can be made efficient both in computation time and space requirements. This confirms its suitability for both software and reconfigurable hardware SAT solvers.

The clauses are viewed as cubes and are subtracted from the n -dimensional Boolean space formed by the variables. The algorithm ends when it finds a satisfying cube or when it proves that the result is an empty set (unsatisfiable formula). The subtraction algorithm is the D-Sharp algorithm, which produces a set of disjoint cubes as the result of subtracting one cube from another. This approach has been implemented in zChaff2004, a state-of-the-art SAT solver and showed good results on Industrial Benchmarks. This seems to be related to the ability to identify a clause or a group of clauses responsible for unsatisfiability, if the problem is UNSAT, or for problem hardness if the problem is SAT.

For future work we intend to tune the clause and variable metrics to work better with the D-Sharp algorithm. We use the metrics already implemented in zChaff. For instance, the age of a clause calculated during UIP conflict analysis is used but recent research has shown benefits of other calculations [15]. Finally, an implementation on reconfigurable hardware is envisaged.

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